

Notebook 1

The group must choose the theme that will be explored throughout all stages of the Speculative Design process, including scenario mapping, the development of speculations, and the outlining of the future intervention.

Group:

chosen theme:

Themes

Theme 1: Dating Apps

Theme 2: Streaming Platforms

Theme 3: Online Betting Platforms

Theme 4: Short-Form Content Platforms

Theme 5: Distance Learning Platforms

Theme 6: Circular Economy Platforms

DATING APPS

Scenario

In the past, romantic encounters were facilitated through in-person interactions, mutual friends, and social events. The emergence of dating apps, such as Tinder in 2012, revolutionized the way people meet and connect, introducing gamification and compatibility algorithms to facilitate matches. These apps brought forth the idea of “long-distance love,” integrating technology into the realm of relationships.

Today, the dating app market is diverse, with platforms that cater to different audiences and needs, ranging from casual connections to long-term relationships.

This speculative design activity proposes the challenge of designing an IT solution for dating applications, focusing on promoting more ethical and responsible interactions. The goal is to minimize negative future impacts, maximize positive and desirable future impacts, and highlight the benefits and technological innovation of the proposed solution.

STREAMING PLATFORMS

Scenario

In the past, the consumption of movies and series was limited to television and video rental stores. The emergence of streaming platforms, such as Netflix in 2007, revolutionized entertainment by allowing users to watch content on demand, anytime and anywhere. These platforms transformed media access by introducing algorithms that recommend content based on user preferences.

Today, the streaming market is vast and highly competitive, offering personalized options for different viewer profiles. Companies continuously seek to evolve their technologies in order to improve the user experience and increase engagement.

This speculative design activity proposes the challenge of designing an IT solution for streaming platforms, with a focus on promoting more ethical and responsible interactions. The goal is to minimize negative future impacts, maximize positive and desirable future impacts, and highlight the benefits and technological innovation of the proposed solution.

ONLINE BETTING PLATFORMS

Scenario

In the past, sports betting was limited to physical betting shops and in-person events. With the emergence of online betting platforms, known as “bets,” there was a significant transformation, allowing users to place bets in real time at any moment. These platforms introduced convenience and a new dynamic to the betting world, using sophisticated algorithms to predict outcomes and offer suggestions to bettors.

Currently, the betting market is vast and highly competitive, with various platforms offering a wide range of sports modalities and even bets on non-sporting events. These companies continue to evolve their technologies while also facing criticism.

This speculative design activity proposes the challenge of designing an IT solution for betting platforms, focusing on promoting more ethical and responsible interactions. The goal is to minimize negative future impacts, maximize positive and desirable future impacts, and highlight the benefits and technological innovation of the proposed solution.

SHORT-FORM CONTENT PLATFORMS

Scenario

In the past, the sharing of memes and short-form content occurred mainly in forums and within more limited social networks. With the emergence of dedicated platforms such as TikTok and Instagram, this format quickly became popular, allowing users to create and consume viral content in real time. These platforms introduced a new dynamic to digital content production by using algorithms to maximize engagement and virality.

Currently, the market for short-form content platforms is vast and competitive, with companies constantly improving their technologies to increase user engagement and extend usage time. However, they also face a range of ethical challenges.

This speculative design activity proposes the challenge of designing an IT solution for short-form content platforms, focusing on promoting more ethical and responsible interactions. The goal is to minimize negative future impacts, maximize positive and desirable future impacts, and highlight the benefits and technological innovation of the proposed solution.

DISTANCE LEARNING PLATFORMS

Scenario

In the past, education was predominantly in-person, limited to physical spaces such as schools and universities. The emergence of distance learning platforms, driven by the internet and digital technologies, transformed access to knowledge, allowing students to learn from anywhere and at any time. Education became more accessible and personalized, especially after the 2020 pandemic.

Today, the distance learning market is in constant growth, with new tools being integrated, such as artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR), and virtual reality (VR) to create immersive learning environments. However, these innovations also raise a series of questions.

This speculative design activity proposes the challenge of designing an IT solution for distance learning platforms, focusing on promoting more ethical and responsible interactions. The goal is to minimize negative future impacts, maximize positive and desirable future impacts, and highlight the benefits and technological innovation of the proposed solution.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY PLATFORMS

Scenario

In the past, consumption was largely based on a linear model, in which products were manufactured, purchased, used, and discarded. With growing environmental concerns and the depletion of natural resources, the concept of the circular economy emerged, aiming to promote the reuse, recycling, and repair of products, extending their useful life cycle and reducing waste.

Today, digital platforms play a fundamental role in facilitating this transition. Applications and platforms for exchanging goods and services, such as eBay, Mercado Livre (Brazil), and Facebook Marketplace, allow people to buy, sell, or trade used products, promoting resource sharing and reuse.

This speculative design activity proposes the challenge of designing an IT solution for circular economy platforms, focusing on promoting the exchange and reuse of goods and services in an ethical and sustainable way. The goal is to minimize negative future impacts, maximize positive and desirable future impacts, and highlight the benefits and technological innovation of the proposed solution.